

A Comparative Analysis of Social Support, Resilience, Life Satisfaction, and Posttraumatic Growth among Cancer Patients, Individuals with Chronic Illness, and Healthy Adults

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The current study compared perceived social support, resilience, life satisfaction, and posttraumatic growth among cancer patients, individuals with chronic non-malignant illnesses, and healthy adults. Our study explored significant mean differences for illness types and main demographic factors, including parental status, sibling presence, and marital status, as well as their interactions with illness type, to find variations in psychosocial resources across health conditions. There were 429 adults aged who were purposively recruited from clinics in Kolkata and surrounding suburban areas, age range 18-60, it includes 149 cancer patients, 168 patients with chronic illnesses, and 112 healthy people without any known diagnosis. Data was collected from individuals with informed consent, and standardized psychological scales were used. Comparative analyses showed that Illness type showed significant effects on perceived life satisfaction, personal strength, new possibilities, and spiritual influence, while the presence of siblings was significantly associated with new possibilities and several resilience dimensions. Further sibling and illness type interactions showed effects on life satisfaction, spiritual growth, and multiple resilience. Similarly, the presence of children significantly influenced perceived social support from friends, improved relationships, and resilience, while illness type significantly affected life satisfaction, resilience components, and several PTG domains. The interaction effects between children and illness type for perceived social support and multiple resilience dimensions were significant. Marital status showed significant effects on perceived social support, PTG domains, and resilience. Family support was affected by illness type. Marital status and illness type interactions were significant for perceived social support, positive acceptance, new possibilities, and spiritual influence.

Keywords: Chronic illness, resilience, posttraumatic growth, perceived social support, life satisfaction

Introduction and Theoretical Background

Long-term diseases like multiple sclerosis, heart disease, or cancer can cause serious mental and emotional strain on patients, affecting their overall health and life quality. Along with the physical impact, these conditions deeply affect psychosocial changes that test people's sense of control, purpose and meaning (Esposito, 2016). In recent years, research has moved to a more inclusive model rather than just highlighting the negative aspects of illness growth, resilience and

personal well-being even in difficult times. This concept shows how people undergo posttraumatic growth (PTG) - a positive mental change that comes from dealing with big life challenges and not just getting used to long-term illness (Zeligman et al., 2018).

Psychological concepts like resilience, social support and life satisfaction are linked here. Resilience is described as the capacity to bounce back from or adapt well to stress and hardship (Seiler & Jenewein, 2019). Resilience acts like a shield against long-lasting illness, which reduces mental suffering and boosts recovery. Research shows that the more resilience, the better the life satisfaction and fewer depression symptoms observed (Adamkovič et al., 2021). Similarly, social support as an ability helps someone to cope and adjust mentally, relying on others for emotional, informational or practical help. Ogińska-Bulik (2013) discovered that social support hugely helps in developing PTG for people dealing with cancer. Thereby, reducing stress and promoting positive thinking during tough times through friendships and connections.

Life satisfaction is an important part of subjective well-being. It shows how people think about their life situations compared to what they expect and value (Diener et al., 1985). New data for those dealing with long-term illnesses indicates that having social support and resilience are two very strong factors that lead to higher life satisfaction (Ruiz-Rodríguez et al., 2022; Brajković et al., 2023). Importantly, these factors do not work alone rather, resilience might

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act as a link between social support and life satisfaction. Good social connections also suggests of boosting people's inner strength to adapt, which in turn makes their well-being better (Wu et al., 2022). Tang et al. (2024) showed that social support and PTG in patients with acute coronary syndrome are completely connected by resilience. Thus, to look at these ideologies in a psychosocial framework becomes important.

Resilience and the feeling of social support work together in a complex way to help people achieve better psychological results when dealing with illness, as is now suggested in many studies. Moreover, resilience helps people to see their traumatic experiences differently, making it part of their life story, which can lead to positive changes after trauma (Tedeschi & Calhoun, 2004). On the other hand, social support gives emotional comfort, which improves resilience. Research involving cancer patients indicated that good connections with family and friend improves emotional recovery and finding new meaning after getting diagnosed (Gu et al., 2023; Ruiz-Rodríguez et al., 2022). Studies dealing with breast cancer survivors further revealed that resilience connects the perceived social support with PTG. This shows that people who feel more support from friends and family tend to cope effectively and experience personal growth (Gu et al., 2023).

At the same time, life satisfaction comes up as both a result and a sign of good adjustment. People with long-term illnesses having more resilience tend to report greater life happiness, despite having physical or treatment limitations (Adamkovič et al., 2021). Additionally, perceived social support works not just as a tool for coping but also as an indicator of personal well-being. Research with cancer patients shows that support from family and friends strongly predicted optimism and life satisfaction (Faraci & Bottaro, 2022). Similar results were seen in patients having spinal cord injuries, showing that backing from family was the strongest predictor for PTG, while happiness in life was predicted by friends' support (Ghannad et al., 2018).

Building on this empirical base, the current study proposes that kind of illness (cancer, chronic non-malignant sickness, or healthy adults) may influence how resilience, perceived social support, life satisfaction and PTG relate to each other. Specifically, because cancer is usually seen as a threat to life and it disrupts one's sense of identity greatly, cancer patients might report more PTG compared to those with long-term chronic diseases. This finding is consistent with past findings, which suggest facing deadly challenges leads to growth via deep reflection about existence and finding meaning (Stanton et al., 2006; Zeligman et al., 2018). People with long-term chronic illnesses, on the other hand, might depend more on ongoing resilience and continuous support from others to keep life satisfaction instead of focusing on personal growth outcomes (Esposito, 2016).

Earlier research showed that relationships with siblings and parents are crucial in acknowledging social resources, finding meaning and helping people cope better while dealing with illnesses (Davies et al., 2018). In tough times, having siblings can improve dealing emotionally, thereby leading to better mental health adjustment (Martire & Schulz, 2007). In the same way, being a parent can increase someone's acceptance and drive for resilience because taking care of children pushes them to cope better (Rolland & Walsh, 2006). So, this study wants to see the impact on resilience and happiness in life of people due to the presence of kids or siblings. It is expected to change depending on the mental challenges and type of illness they face.

Another significant factor is a serious romantic relationship; research studies regularly show that support from a husband, wife, or partner makes individuals stronger, more positive, and predicts improved psychological health for those with long-term illnesses (Bodenmann, 2005; Martire et al., 2010). For people suffering from cancer, being in a marital relationship is especially important. It gives them not just physical care but also emotional support, which boosts their positivity and happiness (Rini & Manne, 2004; Ruiz-Rodríguez et al., 2022). On the other hand, lacking such relationships can make individuals feel less secure and more susceptible to dissatisfaction with life. Therefore, notable differences in resilience, perceived social backing, overall happiness with life and PTG depending on illness kind as well as marital situation can be expected. This concurs with past studies that indicate marital support lessens the mental effect of illness (Bodenmann, 2005; Rolland & Walsh, 2006). Thus, the rationale of the research has been established, and the objectives drawn

Objectives of the Study

- Examine significant group differences in resilience, perceived social support, life satisfaction, and PTG across illness types, the presence of siblings and the interaction between types of illness and the presence of siblings.
- Examine significant group differences in resilience, perceived social support, life satisfaction, and PTG across illness types, the presence of children, and the interaction between types of illness and the presence of children.
- Examine significant group differences in resilience, perceived social support, life satisfaction, and PTG across illness types, their marital status, and the interaction between types of illness and marital status.

Method

Participants

The study included 429 participants aged 18 to 60, purposively selected from clinics in Kolkata and nearby suburban areas. The sample comprised 149 cancer patients, 168 individuals with chronic non-malignant illnesses, and 112 healthy adults with no diagnosed illness. Eligible participants were required to live with family, be fluent in English, and have a confirmed diagnosis, while those with co-morbid psychological diagnoses were excluded. Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Review Board (DRC-AIPSK/ETHICS/A91330421004/2-12/2022). Data collection was done through face to face sessions lasting about 30 minutes, standardized measures and demographic details were covered, ensuring confidentiality, anonymity, data protection, and withdrawal rights at any time.

Measures

Posttraumatic Growth Inventory (PTGI): The PTGI inventory developed by (Tedeschi & Calhoun, 1996) which assesses positive psychological changes following adversity has 21 items across five domains: *Relating to New Possibilities*, *Personal Strength*, *Others*, *Spiritual Change*, and *Appreciation of Life*. 6-point Likert scale rates the items (0 = *I did not experience this change* to 5 = *I experienced this change to a very great degree*). High total scores reflect greater posttraumatic growth with internal consistency ($\alpha = .97$) in this study.

Satisfaction With Life Scale (SWLS) : The SWLS, developed by (Diener et al., 1985) is a 5-item instrument that measures overall life satisfaction. Responses are recorded on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = *strongly disagree* to 7 = *strongly agree*). Higher scores indicate greater satisfaction with life. With an acceptable reliability ($\alpha = .87$) in the present sample.

ConnorDavidson Resilience Scale (CD-RISC-25): Developed by (Connor & Davidson, 2003) Resilience was measured using 25 item scale across five dimensions: *Trust in One's Instincts, Positive Acceptance of Change, Personal Competence, Control, and Spiritual Influences*. Items are rated on a 5-point scale (0 = *not true at all* to 4 = *true nearly all the time*), yielding a total score from 0 to 100. Higher scores indicate stronger resilience. Internal consistency in this study was ($\alpha = .89$).

Multidimensional Scale of Perceived Social Support (MSPSS): The MSPSS, developed by (Zimet et al., 1988) includes 12 items

measuring perceived support from Family, Friends, and Significant Others. Items are scored on a 7-point Likert scale (1 = *very strongly disagree* to 7 = *very strongly agree*). Higher scores represent stronger perceived social support. Subscales and total scores showed high reliability ($\alpha = .88$ -.92).

Procedure

Data collection involved individual, face to face sessions conducted within designated consultation rooms. After obtaining informed consent, participants completed a demographic information sheet followed by standardized psychological measures. Each session lasted approximately 30 minutes. Participants were assured of confidentiality. All data were securely stored and used solely for research purposes in accordance with ethical guidelines.

Results

Table 1

Significant Mean Differences in Resilience, Perceived Social Support, Life Satisfaction, and PTG across Illness Type, the Presence of Siblings and the Interaction between Types of Illness

Variables	Siblings		Illness type		Siblings* Illness type	
	F	p	F	p	F	p
PLSS	0.529	0.467	4.343	0.014**	4.427	0.013**
PSS O	0.180	0.672	0.412	0.663	2.385	0.093
PSS FA	0.931	0.335	1.943	0.145	2.496	0.084
PSS FR	0.0155	0.901	2.643	0.105	0.235	0.790
PS	3.76	0.053	5.59	0.004**	2.03	0.132
NP	5.08	0.025*	4.83	0.008**	2.39	0.093
IR	0.336	0.563	2.379	0.094	1.839	0.160
SG	3.60	0.058	2.48	0.085	3.31	0.038*
AOL	2.56	0.110	2.84	0.059	2.69	0.069
R PA	13.41	<0.001	1.55	0.213	5.67	0.004**
R TI	6.709	0.01**	0.748	0.474	4.236	0.015*
R PC	18.80	<0.001	3.27	0.039*	3.71	0.025*
R C	13.775	<0.001	2.800	0.062	0.866	0.421
R SI	4.12	0.043*	7.27	<0.001	6.73	<0.001

Note. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. PLSS - Perceived Life Satisfaction, PSSO - Social Support from Significant Other, PSSFA- Social Support from Family, PSSFR - Social Support from Friends, PS - Personal Strength, NP - New Possibilities, IR - Improved Relationships, AOL- Appreciation for Life, SG - Spiritual Growth, TI - Trust in one's instincts, R PA - Positive Acceptance, R PC - Personal Competence, R C - Control, R SI - Spiritual Influence.

Table 1 explored whether illness type, presence of siblings and the interaction between these two factors would show any significant group difference across the wide range of psychosocial variables. Illness type showed a significant difference in perceived life satisfaction ($p < .01$), personal strength ($p < .001$), new possibility ($p < .001$), and several dimensions of resilience, including personal competence ($p < .05$) and spiritual influence ($p < .001$). All the dimensions of resilience - perception of newer possibility ($p < .05$), personal acceptance ($p < .001$), trusting instincts ($p < .01$), personal competence ($p < .001$), sense of control ($p < .001$) and spiritual influence ($p < .05$) showed significant

difference between individuals having no sibling vs. those were having siblings, suggesting that presence of siblings may have a greater influence on coping, acceptance, and resource mobilization during a terminal or even in non-malignant chronic illness. Significant interaction effects were observed for perceived life satisfaction ($p < .01$), spiritual growth ($p < .05$), positive acceptance ($p < .01$), trust in one's instinct ($p < .05$), personal competence ($p < .05$), and spiritual influence ($p < .001$). These findings highlight that sibling support often amplifies or buffers the psychological impact of illness in complex and illness-dependent ways.

Table 2

Significant Mean Differences in Resilience, Perceived Social Support, Life Satisfaction, and PTG Across Illness Type, the Presence of Children, and the Interaction between Types of Illness

Variables	Children		Illness type		Children* Illness type	
	F	p	F	p	F	p
PLSS	1.09	<0.29	04.26	<0.015*	1.00	<0.368
PSS O	2.16	<0.14	02.91	<0.056	5.64	<0.004**
PSS FA	0.11	<0.73	02.25	<0.107	1.13	<0.321
PSS FR	10.8	<0.001	01.15	<0.316	0.24	<0.781
PS	3.76	<0.05*	07.53	<0.001	2.29	<0.103
NP	2.10	<0.148	06.55	<0.002**	1.59	<0.206
IR	5.27	<0.02*	03.10	<0.046*	1.07	<0.344
SG	0.77	<0.38	03.77	<0.024*	2.03	<0.132
AOL	0.97	<0.32	04.43	<0.012**	1.32	<0.267
R PA	5.35	<0.02*	04.71	<0.01**	6.64	<0.001
R TI	0.29	<0.59	02.11	<0.121	5.35	<0.005**
R PC	0.2	<0.65	06.44	<0.002**	4.38	<0.013*
R C	13.7	<0.001	02.8	<0.062	0.86	<0.421
R SI	1.79	<0.182	11.8	<0.001	5.69	<0.004**

Note. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. PLSS - Perceived Life Satisfaction, PSSO - Social Support from Significant Other, PSSFA- Social Support from Family, PSSFR - Social Support from Friends, PS - Personal Strength, NP - New Possibilities, IR - Improved Relationships, AOL- Appreciation for Life, SG - Spiritual Growth, TI - Trust in one's instincts, R PA - Positive Acceptance, R PC - Personal Competence, R C - Control, R SI - Spiritual Influence.

Table 2 assessed our second objective to explore the possible significant difference of the presence of children, illness type and the interaction between these two factors on the measured psychological

outcomes. Presence of children showed significant difference across perceived social support from friends ($p < .001$), posttraumatic growth factors such as personal strength ($p < .05$), growth in

Table 3

Significant Mean Differences in Resilience, Perceived Social Support, Life Satisfaction, and PTG Across Illness Type, the Type of Marital Status, and the Interaction between Types of Illness

Variables	Illness type		Marital status		Illness type* Marital status	
	F	p	F	p	F	p
PLSS	2.35	0.09	0.95	0.003**	2.56	0.078
PSS O	1.95	0.14	5.59	0.018*	9.49	<0.001
PSS FA	3.31	0.03*	0.67	0.412	5.083	0.007**
PSS FR	1.29	0.27	4.79	0.029*	1.67	0.190
PS	2.69	0.06	14.41	<0.001	3.36	0.036*
NP	0.9	0.4	7.00	0.008**	3.124	0.045*
IR	0.57	0.56	13.7	<0.001	1.418	0.243
SG	0.29	0.74	4.073	0.04*	0.956	0.385
AOL	0.92	0.39	3.83	0.051	1.326	0.267
R PA	0.93	0.91	8.48	0.004**	6.625	<0.001
R TI	1.43	0.23	7.06	0.008**	2.57	0.078
R PC	0.93	0.39	10.49	0.001**	2.079	0.126
R C	13.7	<0.001	2.800	0.062	0.866	0.421
R SI	1.85	0.15	2.50	0.115	4.39	0.01**

Note. * $p < 0.05$, ** $p < 0.01$, *** $p < 0.001$. PLSS - Perceived Life Satisfaction, PSSO - Social Support from Significant Other, PSSFA- Social Support from Family, PSSFR - Social Support from Friends, PS - Personal Strength, NP - New Possibilities, IR - Improved Relationships, AOL- Appreciation for Life, SG - Spiritual Growth, TI - Trust in one's instincts, R PA - Positive Acceptance, R PC - Personal Competence, R C - Control, R SI - Spiritual Influence.

improved relations ($p < .05$), and factors related to resilience personal acceptance ($p < .05$), and resilience in the sense of control ($p < .001$) indicating that having children may modify relational and emotional growth. Illness type significantly affected PLSS ($p < .01$), multiple posttraumatic growth dimensions-including PS ($p < .001$), NP ($p < .01$), IR ($p < .05$), SG ($p < .05$), and AOL ($p < .0$)-and resilience variables such as R PA ($p < .01$), R PC ($p < .01$), and R SI ($p < .001$). Significant interaction effects between illness type and parental status were evident for PSS O ($p < .01$), R PA ($p < .001$), R-TI ($p < .01$), R-PC ($p < .01$), and R SI ($p < .01$). These interactions suggest that parental responsibilities may alter the psychological experience of illness, particularly in cancer and chronic illness groups.

Table 3 evaluated the third objective of exploring the possible significant group differences across illness type, marital status, and their interaction. There were significant differences between the illness types on perceived social support from family ($p < .05$), and on resilience on the sense of having control over oneself ($p < .001$). Marital status significant mean difference across perceived life satisfaction ($p < 0.01$), support from the others ($p < .05$) and perceived support from friends ($p < .05$). Marital status also demonstrated strong significant difference on personal strength ($p < .001$), perceiving new possibility ($p < .01$), improved relations ($p < .001$), spiritual growth ($p < .05$), and almost all the sub-factors of resilience personal acceptance ($p < .01$), trust in instincts ($p < .01$), and personal competence ($p < .01$), which indicated marriage to be an important source of emotional and practical resources. Significant difference across the interaction between types of illness and marital status were observed for perceived social support constructs - PSS O ($p < .001$), PSS FA ($p < .01$). Also, some significant difference observed on personal strength ($p < .05$), and on perceiving new possibility ($p < .05$). Sub-factors of resilience showed significant differences as well - R PA ($p < .001$), and R SI ($p < .01$).

Discussion

Our findings showed resilience, perceived social support, life satisfaction, and post-traumatic growth (PTG) to be pivotal and affect the types of illness and psychosocial factors such as the presence of siblings, children, and an individual's marital status. Our result therefore, emphasized that the social and relational contexts to play a crucial role in an individual's coping abilities and adapt to illnesses of varied severity.

Resilience, and especially the sub-factor contributing to resilience, was found to impact differently in all the measured psycho-social factors, such as the presence of siblings, having children or not and the marital status and importantly in the measured illness types. Resilience also showed differences in the interaction effects measured between the types of illness and the psycho-social factors. This result has aligned with other recently published articles explaining how individuals with stronger societal connections often demonstrate higher resilience and an adaptive way of coping with the adversities of chronic illness (Lin et al., 2025; Peng et al., 2022). The supportive influence of having siblings and getting support from family members often stems from the assurance of emotional as well as experiential sharing, and assistance in availing instrumental resources (Cutrona, 2000).

Similarly, perceived social support from various societal resources was found to be associated differently among the types of

illnesses measured, the psycho-social factors measured and the interaction between. Recently published articles have also confirmed how perceived social support deters psychological distress, encourages psychological well-being, and determines post-trauma growth among individuals having non-malignant chronic or malignant physical conditions (Dryden-Palmer et al., 2024; Mohammadi et al., 2022). Our results further highlighted that social support from friends and others had been differently influenced in the presence of children in the family and in cases when the individual is in a marital relationship. Articles also show a confusing and complex standpoint on the relation between caregiving roles in complex illness and the availability of social resources (Liu et al., 2020).

Posttraumatic growth was found to be significantly different across malignant and non-malignant forms of illness measured, psycho-social factors and the interaction effect. These findings resonate with the evidence from recently published literature on individuals experiencing chronic illness and experiencing PTG through meaning-making, strengthening interpersonal relationships, and renewed appreciation for life (Prati & Pietrantonio, 2009).

Moreover, the observed interaction effects between illness type and marital status on variables like positive acceptance and personal competence suggest that spousal support and marital satisfaction may reinforce adaptive psychological processes (Luo et al., 2023).

Life satisfaction was also found to be significantly influenced by illness type across all three ANOVA models. Thus, concurs with research which found that illness severity, coping efficacy, and available social resources jointly determine subjective well-being (Zheng et al., 2023). This means that in the current sample, the notion is verified that psychosocial variables like social support and resilience enhance overall quality of life and reduce distress.

Conclusion

The current research could determine the differences across the different essential psychological variables between cancer and chronic patients. The findings revealed that psychosocial outcomes among individuals with chronic illness are a result of a combination of illness type and family context. Significant differences are found across illness types in resilience, post-traumatic growth, and life satisfaction. Perceived social support and adaptive psychological functioning were found to be impacted due to demographic variances in siblings, children, and marital status. Across the illness type (cancer & chronic) presence of close family played a role in resilience and PTG variation.

Practical Implications of the Study

These findings highlight the importance of taking on a family and relationship-focused approach in psychosocial care for those with chronic illness, if not cancer. Actions intended to boost resilience, social backing and growth after trauma should actively involve relatives, especially partners and children, also considering support from siblings, where relevant. Clinicians and policymakers must create psychosocial and recovery programs that are mindful of the illness and family structure since improving the social resources can enhance psychological adaptation and life satisfaction within this group.

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